

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Involuntary Part Time in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022

It decreased on average by 11.58%

Istat calculates the value of involuntary part-time work. The variable is defined as the percentage of employed people who declare they have a part-time job because they have not found a full-time one out of the total number of employed people. The data refers to the period 2018-2022 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of involuntary part-time in 2022. Sardinia is in first place by value of involuntary part-time in 2022 with a value of 16.1, followed by Sicily with a value of 15.7, and by Molise with a value of 13.8. In the middle of the table are Basilicata with a value of 11.5 units, followed by Umbria with a value of 10.5 units and Liguria with a value of 10.3 units. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with a value of 7.7 units, followed by Veneto with a value of 7 units and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 5.5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions for percentage change in involuntary part time between 2018 and 2022. Molise is in first place for percentage change in involuntary part time between 2018 and 2022 with a value equal to 22.12% corresponding to a change from 11.3 in 2018 up to a value of 13.8 units in 2022. Sicily follows with a positive variation corresponding to an amount of 3.29% equal to a variation from an amount of 15.2 units up to 15, 7 units equal to a value of 0.25 units. Sardinia follows with a variation corresponding to an amount of -4.17% equal to a variation from an amount of 16.8 units in 2018 up to a value of 16.1 units in 2022. In the middle of the table is Lazio with a variation equal to an amount of -10.53% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 13.3 units in 2018 up to a value of 11.9 units in 2022. Umbria follows with a variation corresponding to a variation of -12.5% equal to a reduction from 12.00 units in 2018 up to a value of 10.5 units in 2022. And finally the Marche with a variation equal to -13.76% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 10.9 units up to a value of 9.4 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a variation corresponding to an amount of -24.66% equal to a reduction from an amount of 7.3 units equal to a value of 5.5. Veneto follows with a reduction of -27.08% corresponding to a reduction from 9.6 units to a value of 7 units or equal to -2.6 units. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with a variation of -27.36% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 10.6 units to a value of 7.7 units. On average, involuntary part time decreased in the Italian regions by 11.58%, going from an amount of 12.17 units to a value of 10.76 units between 2018 and 2022.

Involuntary part-time in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. Involuntary part-time decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022 with the exception of the Islands. In particular in the North it recorded -22.33%, North West -18.10%, North East -26.26%, Center with -9.52%, South with -4.9%, South with -6.62%. On the islands, the value of involuntary part-time work

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

grew between 2018 and 2022, going from an amount of 15.7 units to a value of 15.8 units or equal to a value of 0.1 units corresponding to +0.64 %.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of three clusters:

- Cluster 1: Liguria, Puglia, Molise, Umbria, Lazio, Tuscany, Campania, Abruzzo, Basilicata;
- Cluster 2: Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Trentino Alto Adige, Marche, Piedmont;
- Cluster 3: Sardinia, Sicily, Calabria.

From the analysis of the clusters the following ordering results: $C3 > C1 > C2$. The dominant cluster or C3 is made up of three southern regions namely Sardinia, Sicily and Calabria. This cluster therefore poses a significant economic, social and geographical issue in the context of the distribution of involuntary part time within the Italian regions. In fact, Sardinia, Sicily and Calabria are southern regions with reduced per capita incomes and significant social issues. The second cluster for the presence of involuntary part-time workers is made up of Cluster 2, i.e. a mixed cluster in which there are southern and central regions and also a northern region, namely Liguria. This cluster therefore confirms the presence of a central-southern dynamic in the administration of involuntary part-time workers. Finally, the cluster with the lowest number of involuntary part-timers is cluster 2 made up of the regions of the Centre-North, further confirming the fact that moving from the south to the north, i.e. from the regions with low per capita income to the regions with high capita it is also possible to reduce the value of involuntary part time.

Conclusions. The value of involuntary part time decreased on average in the Italian regions by an amount equal to -11.58% between 2018 and 2022. However, there are two regions in which the value of involuntary part time has grown, namely Sicily and Molise. However, the data shows the presence of a significant gap between central-southern regions and northern regions in terms of involuntary part-time work. It follows that central-southern labour markets are inefficient compared to northern labour markets. A condition that undermines the conditions of work in southern Italy regardless of the phantom politicized narratives that would like to describe southerners as idle, idlers or anthropologically inferior compared to the learned and noble populations of the North. In reality, the options for southern workers are less interesting, profitable and convenient than the possibilities of northern workers who enjoy more efficient labour markets thanks also to the profitable connections with the rich countries of central Europe.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 2(2), 85-110.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The smes innovation in europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Laureti, Lucio, Alberto Costantiello, and Angelo Leogrande. "THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT." IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics. 2021.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Appendix

